

Stability assessment of thin-walled carbon-reinforced elements with alternating and conventional grid reinforcement

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Abstract

Carbon neutrality demands adoption of alternative construction strategies, departing from the widely used steel-reinforced concrete. Carbon reinforced concrete offers the possibility to build segmented slabs with very thin webs and flanges, therefore reducing the material consumption. However, thinner structural members are susceptible to buckling. The present paper presents six small scale series of compression test. Specimens with a thickness of less than 28 mm are reinforced with different textile carbon reinforcement grids. Two subgroups of manually produced carbon grid reinforcement, one with a novel diagonal branching and merging yarn path, and the other with yarns perpendicular to each other, show significant difference in the stress-strain behaviour. The behavior is non-linear for the first and linear for the second mentioned. In addition, industrial produced biaxial Q85 carbon textile was investigated with warp or weft direction under compression. No influence in the stress-strain behavior was observed. The ultimate stress of the specimens with diagonal reinforcement is 13% and with yarns perpendicular to each other 9% lower than for the biaxial Q85 reinforcement. The results of this study provide a solid foundation for future large-scale investigations.

Keywords: *stability, thin-walled elements, carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRPs) reinforcement, carbon-reinforced concrete, compression test.*

1. Introduction

When concrete is reinforced with carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRPs), the term carbon-reinforced concrete (CRC) applies. CRC offers promising pathways toward sustainable systems, aligning closely with the vision of carbon-neutral construction by 2050 (Curbach et al. 2024). Textile-reinforced concrete or mortar reduces the crack widths for concrete elements and carbon textiles have six times the tensile strength of steel, that require new design strategies for full utilization (Gielis et al. 2024; Spartali et al. 2023). The high tensile strength, corrosion resistance, and lightweight properties of carbon reinforcements enable the design of slender structural elements, which reduce material consumption (Beckmann et al. 2021; Schürmann 2007; Preinstorfer et al. 2019). On the other hand, building thinner raises stability concerns, as phenomena such as buckling occur for elements that are very high or long compared to their thickness (Giese et al. 2023). Buckling is well known from steel construction, where the elastic material enables to determine buckling resistances reliably and design codes provide methods for increasing buckling resistance with transverse stiffeners for example (EN 1993-1-1 2025). Concrete as inhomogeneous material and reinforced with carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP) has not yet been studied in large structural elements. With increasing strength class, the modulus of elasticity rises more slowly in relation to compressive strength (see Figure 1). Buckling occurs for a concrete class of

C20/25 at a slenderness of >120 , whereas it occurs at < 70 for C100/115 (Schmidt 2022). Studies of compression behavior for CRC with conventional reinforcement could not only achieve buckling through various eccentricities, it could also predict the buckling with *Euler's* formula (Giese et al. 2023).

Figure 1. Stress-slenderness diagram of a perfect column for different concrete strength classes (Schmidt 2022) modified.

The ratio of compressive strength to Young's modulus E determines if a structure buckles or not, therefore, the risk of buckling in a component depends not only on its slenderness, but also essentially on its material (Schmidt 2022). This paper investigates small plates under compression in order to determine material-specific buckling behavior. The used reinforcement is manually produced and has a pattern where the yarn guidance starts from top to bottom and is guided back to the top after a horizontal offset, creating a so-called alternating reinforcement (Ur Rehman et al. 2023). Current industry standards predominantly support biaxial grid-like structures with uniform spacing, limiting architectural variations (Kyzymchuk et al. 2025). However, in many cases, component-specific reinforcement designs with curved or net-shaped yarn paths are preferred to align the reinforcement structure with the primary tension trajectories of the component (Curbach et al. 2024; Knippers und Speck 2012; Hu et al. 2013; Younes et al. 2012; Schumann et al. 2024). The structural performance of an alternating reinforcement was investigated in a hollow core slab, but the buckling behavior of the webs requires further investigation (Sandmann et al. 2025). The presented investigation will help to determine the slenderness of large-scale plates and subsequently, ribbed slab systems based on the presented material combination can be built.

2. Material

2.1. Carbon reinforced concrete

A self-compacting concrete with flowability class SF3 according to EN 206-06 table 6, with viscosity class VS2 according to table 7 and a maximum aggregate size of 2 mm was set (EN 206 2013). The Young's modulus $E_{cm} = 45.900 \text{ N/mm}^2$ was determined on cylinders and the characteristic compressive strength of $f_{ck} = 76 \text{ N/mm}^2$ on $4 \times 4 \times 16 \text{ cm}$ prisms. For the mixture, a ready-to-use binding agent concept called *VARIODUR®-C*, which is based on the three main components, namely: portland cement, granulated blast furnace slag and limestone powder, was used herein (Dyckerhoff GmbH 2021). Details about the mixture that was designed as C100/115 can be found in (Giese 2024) and the concrete is classified as C70/85.

Two different types of reinforcement were used. The industrial produced carbon-textile reinforcement is manufactured using highly efficient multiaxial warp knitting technology and consists of closed 2D non-crimp fabrics (NCF) and grid-like NCF structures with uniform grid spacing (Kyzymchuk et al. 2025). Here the biaxial grid from solidian GmbH *Q85-CCE-21* is deployed. The in section 2.2 further described manual produced carbon grid reinforcement consists of carbon fibers (*Tejin Tenax-E STS 40 E23 48 K 3200 tex*) (*F13*) and *SIKA Biresin CR84/CH120-6* serves as impregnation. The latter consists

of epoxy resin and hardener in the mixing ratio 100:28 (solidian GmbH 2024; Sika Deutschland CH AG & Co KG 2025). Determining the tensile strength for the manual produced carbon reinforcement according to DAfStb Heft 660 (DAfStb-guideline 2024) resulted in $f_{f, nm, k} = 741 \text{ N/mm}^2$, statistical details can be found in Table 1.

Table 1. Material properties of high-strength concrete and carbon reinforcement.

Material	Test	Unit	Value	σ^a	CoV ^b
Concrete	Mean compressive strength f_{cm}	MPa	91.9	8.81	0.1
	Characteristic compressive strength f_{ck}	MPa	76.1		
	Mean flexural strength $f_{ctm, fl}$	MPa	10.47	0.35	0.03
	Mean Young's modulus E_{cm}	MPa	45867	901.85	0.02
Manual produced carbon grid reinforcement	Mean tensile strength $f_{f, nm, m}^c$	MPa	1090.6	199.1	0.18
	Characteristic tensile strength $f_{f, nm, k}^c$	MPa	741.1		
Industrial produced biaxial Q85 carbon-textile reinforcement	Mean tensile strength $f_{f, nm, m}^c$	MPa	4070		
	Characteristic tensile strength $f_{f, nm, k}^c$	MPa	3039		

^a Standard deviation

^b Coefficient of variation

^c For fiber cross-sectional area per fiber strand

2.2. Production of the manual produced carbon grid reinforcement

The name alternating reinforcement refers to the diagonal branching and overlapping yarn placement, which is not placed only in one place of a later beam or plate, but alternating its position from the top chord to the bottom chord and continuing to the top again in a branching manner. Carbon reinforced concrete slabs that will be constructed in the near future using thin-walled sheets as a web for a T-cross-section need to resist shear forces and normal forces. The small width would not be able to feature a shear and bending reinforcement with rebars and stirrups in a conventional way. The alternating reinforcement represents both shear and bending reinforcement. As the alternating reinforcement follows a certain pattern, the reinforcement is produced manually. The production, as shown on the left of Figure 2a, consists of a stand and yarn storage, where the virgin carbon fiber is placed, an epoxy impregnation bath with three cylindrical rollers and a restriction at the exit of the bath (allowing the impregnation to be evenly distributed) and a frame where the reinforcement is placed.

Figure 2. Production of alternating carbon reinforcement (© on the right: Stefan Gröschel).

The branching and merging pattern of the alternating reinforcement is described as in Figure 2b, where a carbon yarn arrives from the top, directed diagonally over a horizontal distance of 160 mm to the bottom, where it extends 160 mm horizontally, before being placed back to the top in the same way (principle described as well in (Ur Rehman et al. 2023; Penzel et al. 2023)). The height of the reinforcement is 250 mm, therefore 1 cm of concrete cover on each side of the reinforcement is set for the final specimen height of 270 mm. The angle of the diagonal yarn is 57° and as in the next round of path laying the yarn is placed 40 mm behind the first yarn, 4 yarns overlap in the top and bottom part, as shown in Figure 2b. After manual production of the reinforcement, the frame rested for 24 hours for full curing of the epoxy resin at room temperature, before the dismantling took place. Herby the round profiles of the frame are loosened and then turned inwards, enabling a dismantling with the help of flat tools, going between the frame profile and the reinforcement. In addition to the diagonally alternating path, a reinforcement with yarns perpendicular to each other ($0/90^\circ$), called “straight reinforcement” is generated by placing first unidirectional 0° -oriented yarns continuously over the length, before placing the 90° oriented yarns (see Figure 3a). As no yarns overlap with each other in the top or bottom part, the reinforcement area is a fourth of the alternating reinforcement. The industrial produced biaxial Q85 carbon grid reinforcement existing of so-called warp yarns (0° - in production direction) and weft yarns (90°), is depicted in Figure 3b.

Figure 3a: Manual produced carbon textile reinforcement, b: Industrial produced biaxial carbon textile reinforcement Q85-CCE-21.

3. Experimental program

3.1. Overview

The load adaptation and self-anchorage of yarns were investigated by varying their alignment. The program was divided into three main groups. Group 1 was specimens with manually produced reinforcement. This group was further subdivided into two subgroups: specimens reinforced with alternating and specimens reinforced with straight reinforcement. Group 2 contained specimens with conventionally produced Q85-CCE-21 reinforcement. This group was subdivided into the subgroups: Q85, Q85 weft submitted to compression and Q85 warp submitted to compression. The last two subgroups have a smaller height, creating a comparison with *Giese's* test (Giese et al. 2023). In addition, group 3 represents specimens without reinforcement. For each subgroup, three specimens were tested, so a total of 18 specimens are investigated and presented in Table 2. The dimensions are given as average in the form of Height×Width×Thickness.

Table 2. Matrix of studied parameters.

Group	Reinforcement	Dimension in mm	Number of tests
Manual produced carbon grid reinforcement	Alternating	281×120×21	3
	Straight	280×117×22	3
	Biaxial Q85	292×119×28	3
	Q85 weft (90°)	209×104×27	3

Industrial produced biaxial Q85 carbon textile reinforcement	Q85 warp (0°)	213×105×27	3
None	No reinforcement	279×113×24	3

3.2. Production of concrete specimens

For the manufacturing, thin plates of carbon reinforced concrete with a thickness of $t \approx 22$ mm for the specimens with manual produced reinforcement and $t \approx 27.5$ mm for the specimens with industrial produced biaxial reinforcement Q85 were cast in a formwork of sealed timber with dimensions of 990×430 mm (see Figure 4a). The position of the reinforcement was secured by clamping the textile reinforcement at the edges in between steel clamping strips (in blue in Figure 4a). One day after casting, the small plates were cut from the big plate.

Figure 4a: Casting of big plate with manual produced carbon grid reinforcement, b: Test setup example with specimen containing industrial produced biaxial carbon-textile reinforcement Q85.

3.3. Measuring devices and test setup

The test setup is shown in Figure 4b. On each specimen, four strain gauges with a measuring length of 30 or 60 mm were installed on the surface of the concrete pouring (named: front side) and opposite where the formwork (named: back side) was. On each side, one strain gauge was placed vertically and one horizontally. The k-factor of the strain gauges was 2.13. Load introduction plates, consisting of several high-strength and highly ductile steel bristles, whose deformability minimizes the transverse strain resistance in the concrete sample, were used. The bristles have a length of 80 mm and a cross-sectional area of 4×4 mm². The space between them is approximately 0.2 mm. With a measuring frequency of 5 Hz, the machine force and the machine path were tracked and the loading speed of 0.002 mm/s was path-controlled. After a preliminary force of 200 N for the specimens with manually produced reinforcement in the LFM 600 machine of the Otto-Mohr-Laboratorium, the test started. For the specimens with conventional reinforcement, testing took place in the triaxial machine with a load capacity of 3,000 kN, therefore the preliminary force was 1 kN.

4. Results

4.1. Presentation of failure modes

During the test, the force to machine path behavior was linear, the failure was announced only slightly before the ultimate load by small cracks in the concrete or minor spalling. The failure mode was compression failure. The specimen without any reinforcement is shown in Figure 5a, whereas the

specimens with manual produced reinforcement are shown in Figure 5b-c. The industrial produced biaxial Q85 reinforcement in the specimen after failure is shown in Figure 5d-f.

Figure 5. Image of failure after compression test. a: unreinforced; b: straight manual produced carbon grid reinforcement, c: alternating manual produced carbon grid reinforcement, d: biaxial carbon textile reinforcement Q85, e: carbon textile reinforcement Q85, weft direction submitted to compression, f: biaxial carbon textile reinforcement Q85, warp direction submitted to compression

Comparing the failed specimens with the rectangular specimen from *Giese*, the unreinforced one failed in a similar manner, with the exception of one here tested, which was separated entirely over the height (*Giese* 2024). The specimens with manually produced reinforcement showed spalling in the upper third of the height, whereas the specimens with conventional reinforcement and a height of 29 cm spalled over a longer distance. *Giese's* specimens cracked over half of their height, as could be reproduced for the specimens with conventional reinforcement and a height of 21 cm. All specimens from *Giese* remained in the load introduction, even with significant spalling (*Giese* 2024), which was reproduced for the smaller specimens here but the higher specimens with manually produced reinforcement got pushed out of the load introduction plates due to significant concrete spalling.

4.2. Stress-strain diagram

The strain from vertical strain gauges on both sides of the specimen was used to create the diagrams in Figures 6 and 7. The stress-strain diagrams in the figures present the behaviour of the strain gauges on the front side in a straight line and on the back side in a dashed line. The stress was calculated by dividing

the applied force by the cross-sectional area. The average area of each specimen can be deduced from Table 2.

As shown in Figure 6a, the unreinforced specimens show similar behavior on the front and back side, subsequently the average of the three specimens is represented by the thick grey line in Figure 6b.

The presence of reinforcement influences the stress-strain behaviour, as the difference between the front and back side increases for the reinforced specimens. In Figure 6a the strain measurement on both sides of the specimen for alternating reinforcement differs significantly and in addition, the curve is convex instead of linear. Furthermore, a positive strain is measured at the beginning of the test. These findings vary significantly from *Giese's* findings, assuming that the chosen dimensions already lead to buckling (Giese et al. 2023). In Figure 6b the stress-strain behavior for the specimens with straight reinforcement differs less between the front and back side, and a linear behavior, as for the unreinforced specimens is observed. Higher ultimate stresses and strains were achieved for the specimens reinforced with biaxial carbon textile reinforcement Q85. The behavior of the front side in comparison with the back side differs to the same extent as the specimens with alternating reinforcement.

Figure 6. Stress-strain diagram. a: specimens with alternating reinforcement (manual produced) compared to specimens without reinforcement, b: specimens with straight reinforcement (manual produced) compared to specimens with industrial produced carbon textile reinforcement Q85

The influence of the yarn direction was studied as well with smaller specimens, reinforced with biaxial carbon textile reinforcement Q85. The grid inside the specimens was oriented so that the warp direction or the weft direction was under compression. The stress-strain diagram in Figure 7a shows no significant difference in the two directions regarding the ultimate stress, as well as the pathway of the front and back side. One outlier exists for each series as the behavior is steep and in the positive strain. Comparing the curve of the specimens with Q85 straight reinforcement having a height of 29 cm and the same reinforcement in the specimens with 21 cm in Figure 7b, the ultimate stress and strain is not affected. Regarding the curves of the two sides, it is visible that the behavior of the front side interchanges with the behavior of the back side between the specimens.

Figure 7. Stress-strain diagram. a: specimens with biaxial reinforcement Q85 comparing warp (0°) and weft (90°) direction submitted to compression, b: specimens with biaxial reinforcement comparing different height of specimens

Overall, the specimens with manually manufactured straight reinforcement experiences the most linear behavior. For reproducibility, however, the specimens with conventional Q85 straight reinforcement are assessed further on. In addition, no significant influence in the stress-strain behavior appeared when changing the height of the specimens. Therefore, the specimens with conventional Q85 straight reinforcement and a height of 29 cm are analysed further on.

4.3. Deducing relevant parameters for further stability investigation

As the aim of the small compression test is the determination of the point until the carbon reinforced concrete plates behave linear elastic, the following steps are pursued for the specimens reinforced with conventional Q85 carbon textile, h=29 cm, creating Figure 8:

- Present the curve of stress-strain diagram, averaging front and back side and including all three specimens
- Create the secant modulus of elasticity between the origin of coordinates and 30% of ultimate compression strength (find belonging strain in data)
- Calculate the Young's modulus and determine the strain from which on the secant modulus differs by more than 2% from the stress-strain curve of the specimens (Newman 1966)
- The point of deviation represents the stress until the stress-strain behavior stays linear-elastic (called proportionality limit f_p)
- Trace the line into the diagram of *Euler*, the intersection projected to the x-axis with the slenderness represents the limit slenderness.

The proportionality limit f_p values 39.6 N/mm², which is equivalent to 42% of the compression strength of the material. Therefore, the presented elastic material behavior is close to the behavior of normal concrete, even though the concrete is classified as high-strength concrete. *Mark* states that the change to inelastic behavior of stresses is at 30-40% of f_c (Mark und Schnütgen 2001). The proportionality limit f_p leads to a limit slenderness of 100. Smaller slendernesses lead to inelastic behavior until the slenderness of 60, which represents the slenderness at ultimate compression strength f_c . A slenderness >100 will lead to elastic material behavior, therefore leading to buckling.

Figure 8a: Stress-slenderness diagram with ideal failure line and limit between inelastic and elastic buckling (left) deduced from stress-strain diagram of specimens with Q85 conventional reinforcement (right).

Comparing the results with *Giese*, it is observed initially, that the here presented ultimate stress and strain are smaller, leading to a difference in the modulus of elasticity from $E_{Giese}=43.6 \text{ GPa}$ to $E_{Zierul}=39.8 \text{ GPa}$ (Giese et al. 2023). Secondly, the curves experience convex instead of linear behavior for the single stress-strain curve of the specimens. The method of averaging the front and back side leads to a more linear behavior, which is scrutinized.

5. Conclusion

The investigation showed a different behavior of the concrete specimens with alternating carbon reinforcement ($\pm 57^\circ$) compared to conventional biaxial carbon textile reinforcement Q85 ($0/90^\circ$) submitted to compression. The ultimate stress of the specimens with diagonal reinforcement is 13% and with yarns perpendicular to each other 9% lower than for the biaxial Q85 reinforcement. The yarns for the manual produced alternating carbon grid reinforcement are merging, so that a force on the top of a specimen is transferred to the bottom continuously. The overlapping of the yarns in the cross-section leads to a reduced and unevenly distributed concrete cover and, therefore non-linear strain behavior in the compression test. The production is not yet carried out with a constant tension on the yarn; therefore, the reproducibility can be increased using machine or robot-guided yarn placement.

Whether the warp or weft direction is put under compression does not change the stress-strain behavior of industrial produced biaxial Q85 carbon textile reinforcement. The determined limit slenderness of 100 is the prerequisite for further studies. Testing plates of 1 m length will follow with different thicknesses and support conditions, but using the same mean compression strength of 92 N/mm^2 . Plate buckling will be achieved by using a greater slenderness of 120.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by the Collaborative Research Center SFB/TRR 280 of the German Research Foundation (German: Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft; short: DFG) with grant number 417002380. The authors would like to thank the DFG for supporting the research project.

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